

FROM CERTIFICATES TO CREATION: REPOSITIONING EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS IN NIGERIA TO DRIVE PRODUCT INNOVATION FOR A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

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Abstract

Nigeria's education system prioritizes theoretical knowledge and certificate acquisition, resulting in a workforce ill-prepared for product innovation and sustainable economic growth. This study addresses the disconnect between academic training and practical skills needed for industrial productivity and sustainable development. Through a literature review of academic journals, policy reports, and global case studies, this paper explores how Nigeria's education system can be repositioned to produce graduates capable of creating sustainable products that drive economic growth. Findings reveal that countries emphasizing product development, technical training, and sustainability education achieve higher innovation and self-reliance levels. In contrast, Nigerian graduates often lack essential skills for innovation and leadership. This study concludes that a paradigm shift from certificate-based learning to product-oriented education is crucial. Recommendations include curriculum reform, industry-academia collaboration, and integrating entrepreneurship and sustainability into academic programs. These reforms are vital for transforming education into a catalyst for economic resilience and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Product-Oriented Education, Sustainable Development, Educational Reform, Economic Self-Sufficiency

1 INTRODUCTION

Innovation has emerged as a critical driver of economic productivity, sustainable development, and national competitiveness; countries that incorporate strong innovation systems and invest in green and digital technologies are better placed to convert knowledge into productive, competitive industries. Promoting innovation and economic change is largely based on the growth of vibrant startup communities and the growth of small and medium size enterprises (SMEs). Although there is growing interest in Africa on innovation ecosystems, the continent continues to face significant challenges such as weak infrastructure, inefficient investment in education, and a pervasive skills gap which limit productivity and economic progress (World Bank & OECD/AUC, 2024). The African Union's Agenda 2063 underscores the necessity of developing a skilled workforce

underpinned by science, technology, and innovation as foundational to realizing inclusive and sustainable development (African Union, 2015).” To realize its economic potential, African education systems need to experience a paradigm shift moving beyond certificate-based models, to competency-based, innovation-driven, and entrepreneurship-oriented models.

In Nigeria, the skills gap is also a serious problem. The educational system has often been blamed to have emphasized too strongly on certificate acquisition, creating a culture of rote learning and passing exams instead of critical thinking and hands-on innovation (Okebukola, 2019). This inclination has created generations of graduates who are more credentials-oriented than competency-based to advance industrial productivity. In Nigeria, it was reported that unemployment stood at 5.3% in Q4 2022, while underemployment was 13.7%, with over one-third of employed individuals working fewer than 40 hours per week (NBS, NLFS Q4 2022). These underemployed or partially employed individuals are youth and people with low level of education, group that lack the practical/hands-on skills employers’ demand. Employers continuously report that graduates are not ready to innovate, to become entrepreneurs, or to design a product (Bauman & Lucy, 2021) there is a certain lack of connection between the preparations of higher education institutions and the realities of the labor market (Ibidunni, Ogundana & Okonkwo, 2022). This is due to the fact that Nigeria has one of the lowest historical investments in education. In the years 1980-2000, the nation spent the lowest percentage of its budget on education among similar African countries, even though it was one of the largest economies in the region (Adebayo, 2025). The disregard of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) has also weakened the opportunities of skill acquisition, restricting young individuals to join productive work or innovation-driven businesses (Willie, Umanah, Daniel & Asangausung, 2025; Ahmadu & Orisaremi, 2025). While Nigerian government programs (e.g. the EdTech Summit, EDUREVAMP, and other education-ministry initiatives) have aimed to promote entrepreneurship and innovation in schools, yet challenges persist such as inadequate infrastructure, curricula that lag behind industry needs, and weak school-industry partnerships, which limit reform efforts (Alao, Onah & Alao, 2020). This has led to a systemic issue of the education system in Nigeria; the widening gap between the skills acquired by graduates and the competencies required by the labor market. This misfit creates unemployment, lowers the level of innovation, and does not allow building a startup ecosystem with vitality that can support economic growth. The excessive focus on certificates instead of skills has created a dependency and under achievement cycle that has restricted the competitiveness of Nigeria globally (Soyemi, 2024; Ogbari, Chima, Olarewaju, Olokundun, & Ufua, 2024).

This challenge must be met by a paradigm shift in education, where immediate attention should be given to the repositioning of curricula, pedagogy, and institutional connections; so that they place more emphasis on practical skills, innovation, and entrepreneurship (Igwe, Madichie, Chukwuemeka, Rahman, Ochinanwata & Uzuegbunam, 2022). Therefore, this study, From Certificates to Creation: Repositioning Educational Systems in Nigeria to Drive Product Innovation for a Sustainable Economy seeks to examine how the Nigerian educational system can

be transformed to bridge skill gaps, foster product innovation, and reinforce the foundations of a sustainable and self-reliant economy. The study contributes to existing body of knowledge on education reform and economic progress in Nigeria. The findings provide insight for policymakers, educators, and industry stakeholders on the root causes of the skills gap and possible remedies. By highlighting the importance of entrepreneurship, innovation, and the development of any kind of practical skills, the study will also be used to inform the design of education policy and programs capable of spurring sustainable economic development. Also, the proposed recommendations would be used to close the divide between academia and industry so that the graduates can have the skills and competencies necessary to succeed in the labour market and make significant contributions towards improving the economic resilience of Nigeria.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The present study is based on the Transformative Learning Theory, which was developed by Jack Mezirow, who has been concerned about the role of critical reflection in developing meaningful change among learners. Mezirow (2000) defines transformative learning as a process by which people critically analyse their long held beliefs, assumptions and perspectives to inculcate a radical change in their understanding and actions. Transformative learning is structural, as opposed to surface-level learning, where individuals learn information or technical skills, but transformative learning is more profound and fundamentally alters how one understands oneself, their role and ability to bring about change (Liu, 2020).

Transformative learning theory is also very relevant in the context of the education system in Nigeria, where the present system based on certificates only restricts the learners to memorization and gaining of credentials only, without the development of skills of creativity, innovation, and problem solving (Chukwuemeka, Dominic, Akanbi & Aregbesola, 2025). To be able to really lead to sustainable economic development, the education system needs not only to teach students certain technical knowledge but also to break the existing paradigm of academic success where obtaining a certificate is the only way to achieve it. Ajeniwani, Bamgbowu & Obasi, (2024) stated that transformative learning allows learners to reconsider these assumptions and acknowledge the worth of product-oriented education, entrepreneurship, and the sustainability-based innovation.

Also, Wamsler (2020) stated transformative learning helps in integrating sustainability education through advocating students to perceive the interrelationship between economic, social and environmental systems. It focuses on reflective discourse, problem-solving, and experiential learning which are critical in preparing graduates with skills to develop sustainable products that can fuel the industrial productivity and economic resilience. Using this theory, the research highlights the importance of a paradigm shift in Nigerian education: a shift towards graduates with practical skills rather than job-seekers with certificates. Therefore, transformative learning theory does not only offer a conceptual framework upon which the constraints of the current system can be analysed, but also informs the reforms that are proposed, by showing how education can enable

learners to be critically engaged, adapt and contribute significantly towards sustainable economic growth.

3 METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a conceptual research design, which focuses on theory development and synthesis rather than empirical testing. Following the integrative conceptual review approach recommended by Jaakkola (2020), relevant literature was systematically reviewed from peer-reviewed journals, policy documents, and international development reports addressing education reform, entrepreneurship education, innovation, and sustainable development.

The literature was synthesised thematically around four core areas: (1) educational structure and curriculum orientation, (2) competence and skills development, (3) innovation and entrepreneurship outcomes, and (4) sustainability and economic resilience. Through analytical integration of these themes, patterns, and theoretical linkages were identified.

Propositions were derived through theoretical reasoning, guided by Transformative Learning Theory and supported by recurring insights in the literature. Rather than serving as testable hypotheses, the propositions function as conceptual anchors that structure the framework and guide discussion.

4.0 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND ANALYSIS

Guided by Transformative Learning Theory, this study develops a conceptual framework that explains how Nigeria's education system can move away from an overreliance on certificates toward a more creation-oriented approach to learning. At the core of the framework is the idea that meaningful educational reform is the starting point for this transition. Reforms such as updating curricula, strengthening collaboration between academia and industry, and expanding experiential learning opportunities create the conditions needed for competence-based education to thrive.

Through transformative learning processes, competence-based education enables learners to go beyond memorisation and credential acquisition. Instead, students develop practical technical skills, entrepreneurial capabilities, and sustainability awareness. These competencies are essential for translating education into real-world outcomes, particularly in the form of product development, startup formation, and innovation that supports long-term economic sustainability.

The framework also acknowledges that education reform does not operate in isolation. Its effectiveness depends heavily on the broader institutional environment. Supportive policies, adequate vocational and technical infrastructure, and strong industry partnerships can amplify the impact of competence-based education, while weak institutional support can limit its potential. As illustrated in Figure 1, the framework shows how education reform, when reinforced by institutional support, can act as a catalyst for innovation-driven and sustainable economic transformation in Nigeria.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

4.1 Educational Systems in Nigeria

According to Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013), the Nigerian educational system follows a 6-3-3-4 structure, which involves six years of primary education, three years of junior secondary, three years of senior secondary, and four years of tertiary education. Although this framework was meant to create holistic and skilled graduates, in reality, it has created a more certificate-oriented culture. Historical studies posit that colonial heritage influenced the system to make clerical and administrative employees, instead of innovators or creators (Ouma, 2025; Azhar & Steen, 2023). According to recent studies, systemic challenges include: outdated or overloaded curriculum, insufficient funding, ineffective infrastructure, and reduces the preparedness of teachers to changes, all of which constrain the quality of education and use of innovative pedagogies (Okebukola, 2019; IMF, 2020). These issues contribute to an imbalance between academic education and industry, which restricts the capacity of the Nigerian population to use learning to support economic development.

4.2 Certificate-Driven Education Model

The prevalence of certificates in the Nigerian society is indicative of a general cultural and economic orientation towards qualifications as a means of social mobility in terms of paper qualifications. According to Abiddin and Akinyemi, (2024), this can be characterised as a form of certificate orientation where degrees are the most important indicators of success, which may override actual skills or competence. Employers often provide the requirement of certificates to work at a specific job, even when the graduates have not acquired the real skills related to the work (Okolie, Nwajiuba, Binuomote, Ehiobuche, Igu & Ajoke, 2020). This orientation has limited innovation since individuals are interested in achieving credentials as opposed to building entrepreneurial or technical capacity. In Asia and Europe, comparative studies indicate that economies that have focused more on the competency-based assessment than on certification have been more effective in promoting creativity and industrial competitiveness (Chen, Goncharova, Li & Frommberger, 2024; Sun, 2025). Therefore, the certificate-based system in Nigeria is a structural impediment to an innovation-based growth.

4.3 From Certificates to Creation Paradigm

The shift to creation focuses more on re-positioning education as value creation based on skills, entrepreneurship, and innovation. In this study, creation can be understood as the process of creating not only knowledge but also solutions, products, and services that can respond to the needs of society (Ibidunni, Nwaodu & Mdaka, 2023). Comparative research demonstrates that Finland and other countries like Singapore have transformed their education systems into more competency oriented, creative, and innovative models with high returns to the economy (Bauman, & Lucy, 2021; Chen, et al. 2024). Equally, Nigeria still generates graduates with little creativity, thus perpetuating reliance on employment in the state sector. The paradigm shift thus seeks to incorporate creativity, problem-solving, and entrepreneurial thinking within every level of learning so that learning results in innovators and not certificate-holders.

4.4 Innovation and Product Innovation

Innovation is generally characterised as the adoption of new or substantially better processes, products, or services (OECD, 2018). Product innovation is especially essential within this range since it is a direct determinant of industrial competitiveness and economic growth. Research shows that African economies, such as Nigeria, are underperforming in terms of product innovation as they have low research potential, inadequate industry-university relationship, and lack of investment in research and development (Wamsler, 2020). In contrast, those countries where robust innovation ecosystems were institutionalized, like South Korea, quickly turned into agrarian and then industrialized economies due to their tendency to diversify products and adapt to the latest technologies (Ibidunni, Iyiola & Ibidunni, 2014). In the case of Nigeria, product innovation is crucial as it not only diversifies its economy without relying on oil but also helps in the realization of long-term sustainability.

4.5 Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Education

Entrepreneurship education has emerged as one of the main factors that influence creativity, innovation, and self-employment across new economies. In Nigeria, entrepreneurship studies have been introduced in universities since 2006, but the effects are still weak because of the low implementation rates and ineffective orientation (Olokundun, et al. 2018). Empirical evidence demonstrates that students that go through practical training in entrepreneurship acquire better problem-solving skills, innovation skills, and job skills (Ogbari, et al. 2024; Ezeh and Okafor, 2022). Comparative data on the European Union show that well-organized entrepreneurial education enhances a greater rate of start-ups and positive ecosystems (Volkman et al., 2021). Therefore, sound entrepreneurship education may act as an essential bridge between industrial innovation and academic learning in Nigeria.

4.6 Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET)

Technical and vocational education is generally recognised as one of the pillars of skills development and innovation. The International Labour Organisation, (2020) highlights that the stronger the TVET system is, the higher the preparedness of the workforce and the decreased level of unemployment. The TVET sector in Nigeria is, however, characterized by poor funding, ineffective infrastructure, and stigmatization in society (Okebukola, 2019). Research indicates that the skills of vocational graduates are largely irrelevant to the industry, as the curricula are not aligned with labour market requirements (Ibidunni, et al. 2022). Examples of comparative models that may be used to guarantee that TVET can spur practical innovation and entrepreneurship include the dual training system in Germany and the technical institutes in Singapore (Maclean, 2013). Enhancing Nigeria's TVET is therefore important for bridging the skills gap and driving product innovation.

4.8 Sustainable Economy

A sustainable economy can be described as one that is conducive in terms of inclusive growth and maintaining environmental and social systems to benefit future generations (Ashraf, 2023). Education serves as the focus in developing such an economy since it prepares citizens with the skills and the mindset towards sustainable production, innovation, and entrepreneurship. The connection between education reform and sustainability is also strengthened in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG 4 (quality education), SDG 8 (decent work and economic growth), and SDG 9 (industry, innovation, and infrastructure). Evidence in China and the EU demonstrates that an innovation-based education system leads to faster sustainability achieved through the promotion of green technologies, circular economies, and diversification of industries (Alao, et al. 2020). In the case of Nigeria, innovation-focused education reform is therefore essential in having a sustainable economy.

4.9 Skills Gap Concept

The skills gap can be defined as the disconnect between skills learned by graduates at school and those demanded by employers. Dada, (2019) stated that in Nigeria, studies confirm that while graduates excel in theoretical knowledge, they often lack digital literacy, critical thinking, and entrepreneurial abilities. This mismatch is a major cause of high unemployment and underemployment of graduates. South African and Kenyan evidence of comparative benefit demonstrates that skills gaps can be reduced with enhanced efforts on curriculum reform and greater engagement between universities and the industry (Ngcwangu, 2019). To bridge the skills gap in Nigeria, there is need to instill innovation, entrepreneurship and technical training at all levels of education.

4.10 Education–Innovation Nexus

The connection between innovation and education is being increasingly realized as crucial to national development. Education offers human capital that drives innovation, whereas innovation keeps education in line with labor market and societal demands (Chukwuemeka, et al 2025). Research indicates that curriculum reform, changes in pedagogy, and institutional collaboration would provide a virtuous cycle where education would be the driver of innovation, and innovation would be the driver of education (Law, 2022; Adeoye, et al. 2023). For Nigeria, enhancing the education-innovation nexus is crucial in dealing with skills gap, entrepreneurship, and the attainment of sustainable economic development.

4 DISCUSSION

The findings of this study show that the education system of Nigeria is currently not aligned with the requirements of an innovation-driven economy. The findings are framed within the Transformative Learning Theory, which suggests that the current certificate-driven paradigm is limiting in nurturing real-world competency, entrepreneurialism, and innovation which are critical components of long-term economic growth. The discussions of findings are explained using the developed propositions by the researcher.

Proposition One: Nigeria's skills gap reflects structural, curricular, and pedagogical deficiencies in its education system

The findings support the proposition. Years of emphasis on rote learning and certificate acquisition have resulted in the poorly prepared graduates (Okebukola, 2019). Problem-solving capacity, critical thinking, and technical skills are the skills that are constantly absent among graduates according to employers (Ibidunni, Ogundana & Okonkwo, 2022). These gaps are attributed to archaic curriculum, inefficient pedagogical practices and lack of industrial involvement. Comparative analysis in Asia and Europe demonstrates that competency-based models are more successful in preparing graduates to be innovative and competitive in the industry

(Chen et al., 2024). In the case of Nigeria, the structural weaknesses that have existed over time affirm that skills gap is not an accidental phenomenon but rather a systematic issue that cannot be addressed through an incremental reformation but through a transformational reform.

Proposition Two: Prioritizing skills, innovation, and entrepreneurship in education will enhance product innovation and sustainable growth.

This proposition is also supported by the findings of this study. the study found that countries like Finland, Singapore, and South Korea show that education reform based on creativity and entrepreneurship sparks high product innovation rates and industrial growth (Bauman and Lucy, 2021; Ibidunni et al., 2014). Dependence on certificates has instead created a dependency culture and has limited the capacity of Nigeria to diversify beyond oil. The study establishes that rebranding Nigerian education as a skills-based, innovation-driven, and entrepreneurial enterprise has the potential to deliver a game changer: the graduates will be capable of developing solutions, developing businesses, and creating their own, locally relevant products. This would not only reduce the unemployment gap, but lead to green technologies, digital industries and SMEs which are vital to a sustainable economy.

Figure 2: Comparative Strengths of TVET Systems in Germany, Singapore, Finland & Nigeria

	Industry Collaboration	Hands-on Training	Curriculum Updates
Germany	Dual System: apprenticeships with industry partners	Mandatory internships, practical projects	Regular updates with industry
Singapore	SkillsFuture Program: industry-led training initi-	Industry attachments, internships	Emphasis on lifelong learning
Finland	Mandatory Industry placements, local advisory boards	Real-world projects, competence-based learning	Highly qualified teachers, autonomy for VET providers
Nigeria	Limited industry partnerships, outdated curricula	Infrequent updates lacking industry input	Need for stronger TVET infrastructure, instructor training

Key takeaways for Nigeria:

- **Strengthen industry partnerships:** Establish formal collaborations with industries to provide apprenticeships, internships, and job placements
- **Increase hands-on training:** Integrate more practical projects and real-world experiences into technical education programs. Invest in TVET infrastructure. Provide modern equipment, facilities, and instructor training to support high-quality technical education.

Proposition Three: Entrepreneurship education, TVET, and innovation are vital to bridging skills gaps and driving development.

The finding supports this proposition. Entrepreneurship education was introduced since 2006; its application has been mostly theoretical which has been producing limited impact (Olokundun et al., 2018). In contrast global studies show that hands-on entrepreneurship training generates greater innovation and start-up formation in the world (Volkman et al., 2021). Similarly, the TVET industry in Nigeria lacks adequate funding, infrastructure, and social stigmatization (Okebukola, 2019). This has made it ineffective in providing industry-prepared graduates. Comparative lessons from Germany and Singapore show that re-invented TVET, with a more focus on labour market needs, can be a potent engine of innovation and inclusive development (Maclean, 2013).

Taken together, the findings indicate that the excessive dependency on certificates in Nigeria is an institutional barrier to innovation and sustainable development. Transformative learning, which emphasise reflection, critical inquiry, and experiential knowledge, represents a possible solution to reform. If the educational system is restructured towards creation-focused as compared to credentials, then Nigeria can no longer be a producer of job-seekers but a producer of innovators and entrepreneurs. The findings also show a paradox that while government-led efforts (e.g., EDUREVAMP, EdTech Summit) aim at encouraging innovation, the effectiveness of these efforts is undermined by systemic inertia in curriculum reform, school-industry partnership, and poor long-term underinvestment. Reform should therefore be systematic and inclusive, as opposed to being fragmented in order to bridge the skills gap and ensure education delivers its potentials in the form of sustainable economic development.

5 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Establish the conclusions and make recommendations for future research.

This study offers both theoretical and practical contributions. Theoretically, it builds on the discussion of education reform in Africa by introducing Transformative Learning Theory to describe how the certificate-based model in Nigeria perpetuates the skills gap and limits innovation. The study contributes to the knowledge of competency-based learning and entrepreneurial training as the foundation of sustainable development by framing education as a transition between credentialism and creation.

Practically, the findings offer several implications to policy makers, educators and stakeholders of the industry. At the **policy level**, the findings show that Nigeria chronic skills gap illustrates the urgent needs of system-wide reforms, which extends beyond curriculum changes, resulting in pedagogy, governance, and institutional culture changes. Competency-based learning, with a focus on a critical thinking skill, creativity, digital literacy, and problem-solving as the core learning outcomes, should be explicitly prioritized in the education policies. There should be sustained investment in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) by government and regulatory bodies. This involves not just investing in it but rebranding TVET as an innovation and

entrepreneurship opportunity, less stigma in the society and matching training measures to labour market needs.

At the **institutional level**, strong collaboration with industry is essential to make sure that the curricula are dynamic and responsive to new technologies and changes in the market. Entrepreneurship education should move to models centered on practice Incubation hubs, university–industry partnerships, and mentorship programmes can nurture an entrepreneurial culture from early stages of education. Also, universities and colleges should be encouraged to create innovation labs and accelerator programs to connect students with the real-world product development and start-up environments. There is a pressing need to **de-emphasize credentialism** at stakeholder's level. Employers and professional associations need to transform the recruitment methods toward credentialism to competency-based practice. This could be achieved through government-supported initiatives such as practical skills testing, portfolio-based evaluation, and industry-recognized certifications integrated into both education and employment systems.

Lastly, the need to develop a sustainable economy requires the integration of education reform with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which include SDGs 4, 8, and 9. Embedding green skills, digital innovation, and entrepreneurship within education framework will help decrease unemployment rates besides making Nigeria a regional leader in sustainability-oriented industries. Overall, the finding calls for a multi-stakeholder action. Nigeria can cultivate a job market that that drives innovation, build economic resilience, and advance inclusive sustainable development by repositioning its education as a pathway to creation rather than credentials.

6 LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

This study examines how Nigeria's education system, historically shaped by certificate-orientation, can be repositioned to drive product innovation and support a sustainable economy. Findings of the study show that certificate-based education system in Nigeria is organically incompatible with the requirements of an innovation-based economy. The system perpetuates a long-run skills gap, reducing industry productivity, and limiting competitiveness through prioritisation of credentials over competencies. It is therefore necessary to reposition education to competency-based learning, entrepreneurship, rejuvenated TVET, and enhanced university–industry partnerships. Reforms should also be aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 4, 8, and 9) so that the pathways to inclusive growth and sustainability become even stronger.

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. This research is limited by its use of conceptual framework and secondary data, which might not be a comprehensive reflection of the lived realities of students, employers and educators. It is also limited in generalizability as it

focuses on Nigeria, and the impact of digital transformation, green innovation, and the dynamics of governance is under-researched.

These limitations point to promising avenues for future research. Further research should adopt empirical and comparative methodological approach to prove these propositions, investigate the effects of digital and green technologies, and discuss the governance issues that shape reform outcomes (Ojetunde & Ramnarain, 2023; Anyanwu 2023). Such inquiries would deepen understanding of how education can be repositioned as a catalyst for product innovation and long-term economic resilience.

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